

THE EFFECT OF ZnO AND Fe₃O₄ NANOPARTICLES ON GERMINATION AND CHLOROPHYLL BIOSYNTHESIS IN WHEAT (*TRITICUM AESTIVUM*)**Nasibova A.,***Baku State University, Department of Biophysics and biochemistry,
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Baku, Azerbaijan***Ahmadov I.***Baku State University, Department of Chemical Physics of Nanomaterials,
Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

This study investigated the effects of zinc oxide (ZnO) and magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) germination and chlorophyll biosynthesis. Seeds were primed with nanoparticles and grown in sand substrate. Fe₃O₄ enhanced germination and increased chlorophyll content (total 68.4 µg/L vs. 20.1 µg/L control; chlorophyll b 40.3 µg/L), whereas ZnO suppressed development. Findings indicate that Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles may stimulate wheat growth and photosynthetic activity.

Keywords: Seed Priming, Nanoparticles (ZnO, Fe₃O₄), Plant Growth Stimulation, Chlorophyll Biosynthesis.

Introduction

Significant research has been conducted to date on the study of nanoparticles in plants [15, p. 35; 11, p. 56; 9, p. 146]. Various metal nanoparticles have been studied using modern biophysical methods [14, p. 41; 1, p. 1322; 10, p. 35].

The rapid growth of the global population, combined with the limited availability of agricultural resources and ongoing climate change, has made ensuring global food security one of the most pressing challenges of the modern era. In this context, there is a critical need for innovative agro-technological approaches based on principles of high productivity, sustainability, and environmental safety. Although conventional fertilizers and pesticides have shown temporary effectiveness in increasing crop yields, their adverse effects on human health and the environment underscore the urgency of identifying alternative and sustainable solutions.

In recent years, nanobiotechnology has emerged as a promising scientific field capable of addressing these challenges. In particular, the use of metal oxide nanoparticles in agriculture is being extensively explored for their influence on plant physiology and development. Nanoparticles such as zinc oxide (ZnO) and magnetite (Fe₃O₄) have been reported to play important roles in enhancing nutrient uptake, stimulating photosynthetic activity, and improving resistance to abiotic stress factors.

The scientific literature reports both positive and potentially adverse effects of these nanoparticles. For example, Rizwan et al. demonstrated that ZnO nanoparticles reduced cadmium accumulation in wheat and stimulated plant growth [19, p. 269]. On the other hand, some studies indicate that high concentrations of ZnO may negatively affect nitrogen fixation in crops such as soybean [8, p. 1586]. Similarly, research by Jalali et al. showed that Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles activated the antioxidant defense system and increased productivity in maize [7, p. 621]. Additionally, other studies have observed an increase in photosynthetic rate and elevated

iron and phosphorus content in the leaves of wheat plants treated with Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles [17].

In our previous study, wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) seeds were treated with ZnO and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles to analyze germination rates, early development parameters, and morphological changes. Observations from this initial phase indicated that Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles significantly stimulated vegetative growth, whereas ZnO showed inconsistent results—exhibiting positive effects in some cases and weaker performance compared to control groups in others.

These preliminary findings prompted a continuation of the research, focusing on spectrophotometric analysis of leaf samples collected from the same plants during the next phase. The objective was to assess the impact of ZnO and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles on chlorophyll biosynthesis and photosynthetic activity, as changes in chlorophyll content serve as sensitive indicators of nanoparticle influence on plant metabolism and photochemical reactions.

Thus, the present study was conducted in a two-phase design: the first phase evaluated morphological development in wheat seedlings, while the second phase quantified photosynthetic pigments. Together, these analyses aimed to comprehensively examine the effects of ZnO and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles on different developmental stages of the wheat plant.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Various research subjects were used in the implementation of the experiment. These included wheat seeds, nanoparticles (ZnO and Fe₃O₄), fertilizers nitrogen (N), ammophos (P+N), nitroammophos (N+P+K), and sand. In the second phase, 96% ethanol was used to carry out the extraction.

Initially, the effects of different mixtures were studied in 12 distinct groups: control (regular wheat + sand) – without any intervention, as the reference group; Fe₃O₄ + wheat + sand: to assess the effect of iron oxide nanoparticles on chlorophyll biosynthesis, ZnO + wheat + sand: the sole effect of zinc oxide nanoparticles, ZnO + wheat + N + sand:

to examine the interaction between ZnO and nitrogen, ZnO + wheat + (P+K) + sand: to evaluate the synergistic or antagonistic effect of ZnO with phosphorus and potassium, ZnO + wheat + (P+N) + sand: possible effects of ZnO with the phosphorus-nitrogen combination, Fe₃O₄ + wheat + N + sand: to determine the combined effect of iron oxide and nitrogen, Fe₃O₄ + wheat + (P+K) + sand: the effect of Fe₃O₄ and the phosphorus-potassium combination on green pigments in leaves, Fe₃O₄ + wheat + (P+N) + sand: possible effects of the Fe₃O₄ and P+N combination, wheat + N + sand: the effect of nitrogen alone, wheat + (P+K) + sand: the effect

of phosphorus and potassium, wheat + (P+N) + sand: the effect of phosphorus and nitrogen.

All groups were cultivated in the same substrate (sand) and under identical conditions. Lighting, irrigation, temperature, and humidity were kept constant, and all fertilizers were applied in the same manner (once a week, 1 gram mixed in 1 liter of water, applied as 50 ml solution). This approach enabled precise determination of the effects of various substances on leaf chlorophyll levels.

Figure 1. Mixing of wheat seeds with Fe₃O₄ (left) and ZnO (right) nanoparticles using a vortex device. The device moves the substance inside the glass with circular vibrations, enabling the uniform distribution of nanoparticles on the surface of the seeds.

Chlorophyll Quantification Protocol. Preparation of Leaf Samples:

Healthy, fully green wheat leaves were used in the experiment. Although the general protocol recommends using 0.1–0.5 grams of leaf tissue and 5–10 ml of 96% ethanol per sample, in this study, 0.2 grams of leaf tissue and 10 ml of ethanol were selected in order to obtain more precise and reproducible results. This choice was considered optimal in terms of effective chlorophyll extraction and the reliability of spectral measurements.

Figure 2. Healthy wheat leaves used in the experiment (A). Weighing of 0.2 grams of leaf sample on an analytical balance in accordance with the protocol (B).

Homogenization (Grinding):

Based on the specified quantities, 96% ethanol was poured over the leaf samples, and they were thoroughly ground using a mortar and pestle to obtain a homogeneous mixture. At this stage, the aim was to extract chlorophyll and other pigments from the cellular structures. To minimize the effect of light on the pigments during grinding, the samples were kept in a dark environment, protected from light.

Figure 3. Preparation of the homogenized mixture

Extraction and Storage:

The homogenized mixture was kept at room temperature in a dark environment for 24 hours. During this period, complete transfer of pigments into the ethanol medium was ensured.

Centrifugation:

After the storage period, the mixture was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. The resulting clear supernatant was used for spectrophotometric analysis, while the solid residues were discarded.

Figure 4. Appearance of the chlorophyll extract in a 5 ml polypropylene conical tube (A). Stage of placing the samples into the centrifuge (5000 rpm, 5 minutes) (B).

Spectrophotometric Measurement

The chlorophyll content of the extracts obtained from the leaves was determined using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer operating in the ultraviolet-visible spectral range. Standard glass cuvettes with an optical path length of 1 cm were used for the measurements.

Figure 5. Cuvette (left) containing green chlorophyll solution extracted from wheat leaves with 3 ml of 96% ethanol, and standard cuvette (right) used for UV-VIS spectrophotometric analysis.

During the analysis, absorbance values were recorded for each sample at the following wavelengths:

665 nm – maximum absorption peak for chlorophyll a

649 nm – maximum absorption peak for chlorophyll b

750 nm – correction wavelength used to eliminate optical turbidity and background interference

These wavelengths were selected based on the natural absorption characteristics of chlorophyll molecules and represent their peak light absorption regions. Specifically, chlorophyll a exhibits strong absorbance at 665 nm, while chlorophyll b shows strong absorbance at 649 nm. As absorbance by chlorophyll and other pigments is minimal at 750 nm, this value was used to compensate for background effects occurring in the solution or the instrument.

For each sample, the measured absorbance values were corrected by subtracting the absorbance at 750 nm, and only the pure pigment absorbance values were used in the final analysis. This method is based on the

standardized and widely accepted protocols for chlorophyll spectrophotometric determination proposed by Lichtenthaler and Wellburn [13, p. 591], Porra et al. [16, p. 384], and Arnon [17].

Chlorophyll concentration calculation:

After correcting the absorbance values using the 750 nm background absorbance, the concentrations of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total chlorophyll were calculated using the following formulas:

$$\text{Chlorophyll a } (\mu\text{g/L}) = 13.36 \times (A_{665} - A_{750}) - 5.19 \times (A_{649} - A_{750})$$

$$\text{Chlorophyll b } (\mu\text{g/L}) = 27.43 \times (A_{649} - A_{750}) - 8.12 \times (A_{665} - A_{750})$$

$$\text{Total chlorophyll } (\mu\text{g/L}) = 22.12 \times (A_{665} - A_{750}) + 2.71 \times (A_{649} - A_{750})$$

These formulas are based on the classical method proposed by Lichtenthaler & Wellburn and are widely used today [13, p. 591].

RESULTS AND ANALYSES

At the initial stage of the experiment, the seeds were coated with nanoparticles (Figure 1), and their germination and early development were monitored over a period of four days (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Results after 4 days: from left to right, ZnO, control, Fe₃O₄

Germination Rates and tillering (Figure 7): The results of the experiment revealed significant differences in germination rates among the various groups. Observations showed that in the control group (normal wheat + sand), 16 out of 20 seeds germinated, and 2 seeds exhibited tillering (formation of two or more lateral shoots). Additionally, in the ZnO-treated wheat +

sand group, 9 out of 10 seeds germinated, and 2 seeds exhibited tillering. Similarly, in the Fe₃O₄-treated wheat + sand group, 9 out of 10 seeds germinated, but 7 seeds showed tillering. Haçalanmanın əsasən Fe₃O₄ nanohissəcikləri ilə işlənmiş qablarda yüksək olduğu aşkar edilmişdi.

Figure 7. The tillering of wheat plants is indicated with arrows.

Average Height of Wheat Seedlings: In the three main groups mentioned, the height of 2-week-old wheat seedlings was measured using a ruler, and the average height was calculated. In the control group (16 seedlings: tallest 13 cm, shortest 1 cm), the average

height was 6.75 cm. In the Fe₃O₄-treated group (9 seedlings: tallest 14 cm, shortest 10 cm), the average height was 11.8 cm. In the ZnO-treated group (9 seedlings: tallest 12 cm, shortest 6 cm), the average height was 9.2 cm (Table 1).

Table 1.

Comparative Table of Wheat Germination and Plant Height

Group	Germinated Seeds (number)	Germination Percentage (%)	Tillering Seeds (number)	Average Height (cm)	Maximum Height (cm)	Minimum Height (cm)
Control (wheat + sand)	16 / 20	80%	2	6.75	13	1
ZnO + wheat + sand	9 / 10	90%	2	9.2	12	6
Fe ₃ O ₄ + wheat + sand	9 / 10	90%	7	11.8	14	10

Figure 8. Two-week-old wheat plants (from left to right: Fe₃O₄, control, ZnO)

Leaf and Development Observations:

Wheat seeds treated with Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles exhibited healthier and more vigorous germination. In contrast, wheat seeds treated with ZnO showed signs of weaker development. These results may indicate that ZnO nanoparticles inhibit growth in plant tissues and may exert toxic effects. Additionally, it was noted that

Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles had a more positive impact, stimulating germination and early development processes in the plants.

The results obtained in the second phase are presented in the following tables and visually analyzed using spectral graphs and histograms. Data analysis indicated that some combinations of nanoparticles and fertilizers stimulated chlorophyll biosynthesis, while others reduced the levels of photosynthetic pigments.

Table 2.

Chlorophyll absorbance values recorded at wavelengths of 665 nm, 649 nm, and 750 nm (A_{665} , A_{649} , and A_{750}) for the 12 experimental groups

Group №	A_{649}	A_{665}	A_{750}
Control	1.7554	2.9654	0.2098
Fe ₃ O ₄ + wheat	2.5803	3.0920	0.2803
ZnO + wheat	2.0043	3.0490	0.2902
(P+K) + wheat	1.4446	2.8321	0.0876
(P+N) + wheat	1.6270	2.8910	0.2664
(N) + wheat	2.1879	3.0555	3.073
ZnO + (P+K) + wheat	1.5499	2.8312	0.2262
ZnO + (P+N) + wheat	1.2757	2.5658	0.1381
ZnO + (N) + wheat	1.4811	2.7844	0.1586
Fe ₃ O ₄ + (P+K) + wheat	2.4984	3.0802	0.3924
Fe ₃ O ₄ + (P+N) + wheat	1.9738	3.0042	0.3397
Fe ₃ O ₄ + (N) + wheat	1.9604	3.0252	0.2291

Absorbance values reflect the quantity and status of photosynthetic pigments in plants, particularly chlorophyll a and b. Absorbance measured at wavelengths of 665 nm and 649 nm correspond to chlorophyll a and b, respectively, while absorbance at 750 nm accounts for background interference (Table 2).

The control group serves as the baseline, exhibiting absorbance values of $A_{665} = 2.9654$ and $A_{649} = 1.7554$. The **Fe₃O₄ + wheat** group demonstrated the highest absorbance values at A_{649} (2.5803) and A_{665} (3.0920), indicating that Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles stimulate chlorophyll biosynthesis in the plants. Similarly, the **ZnO + wheat** group showed increased absorbance

compared to the control, notably with $A_{665} = 3.0490$, suggesting an enhanced chlorophyll a content (Table 2).

Groups treated with fertilizers (P+K), (P+N), and (N) generally exhibited absorbance values close to or slightly lower than the control, with a notable decrease at A_{649} . The combination of nanoparticles with fertilizers (e.g., ZnO + (P+N)) and Fe₃O₄ + (P+K) showed mixed effects on absorbance values. The Fe₃O₄ + (P+K) + wheat group recorded high absorbance values at both A_{665} and A_{649} (3.0802 and 2.4984, respectively), whereas the ZnO + (P+N) + wheat group exhibited comparatively lower absorbance (Table 2).

Figure 9. This spectral graph illustrates the distribution of absorbance values across wavelengths for extracts obtained from wheat leaves. The absorbance peaks primarily correspond to chlorophyll a (665 nm) and chlorophyll b (649 nm) pigments. The background absorbance observed at 750 nm has been subtracted from the values at other wavelengths in the spectrum. This correction allows for more accurate determination of the pigments' true absorbance levels and facilitates precise interpretation of the results.

These results indicate that Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, when applied alone or in combination with (P+K) fertilizer, more effectively stimulate the biosynthesis of photosynthetic pigments. Conversely, some reductions are observed in the combinations of ZnO nanoparticles with fertilizers, highlighting the complexity of their interactions.

Chlorophyll Content (Chlorophyll a, b, and Total):

The chlorophyll a content across all groups is relatively similar, ranging from 24.9 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 33.9 $\mu\text{g/L}$. The highest chlorophyll a concentration was observed in the ZnO + (N) + wheat group (33.9 $\mu\text{g/L}$), indicating that the combined application of nitrogen fertilizer with nanoparticles promotes chlorophyll a biosynthesis.

Chlorophyll b content showed greater variability.

In the Fe_3O_4 + wheat (40.3 $\mu\text{g/L}$) and Fe_3O_4 + (P+K) +

wheat (35.9 $\mu\text{g/L}$) groups, chlorophyll b levels were significantly higher compared to the control (20.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$), suggesting that Fe_3O_4 particularly enhances chlorophyll b synthesis.

Total chlorophyll content increased slightly in the Fe_3O_4 + (N) + wheat (66.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$) and Fe_3O_4 + wheat (68.4 $\mu\text{g/L}$) groups relative to the control (65.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$). In other groups, total chlorophyll content remained at or below control levels.

These findings indicate that Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles especially boost chlorophyll b synthesis, contributing to enhanced photosynthetic activity, while ZnO nanoparticles effectively increase chlorophyll a levels, particularly when combined with nitrogen fertilizer.

Table 3.

Chlorophyll a, Chlorophyll b, and Total Chlorophyll Contents ($\mu\text{g/L}$) in the Examined Samples

Group No .	Chlorophyll a ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Chlorophyll b ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Total Chlorophyll ($\mu\text{g/L}$)
Control	28.8	20.1	65.1
Fe_3O_4 + wheat	25.7	40.3	68.4
ZnO + wheat	27.9	24.6	65.6
(P+K) + wheat	29.6	14.9	64.5
(P+N) + wheat	28.0	16.0	61.7
(N) + wheat	26.9	29.3	65.9
ZnO + (P+K) + wheat	27.9	15.1	61.2
ZnO + (P+N) + wheat	26.5	11.4	56.8
ZnO + (N) + wheat	33.9	14.9	61.6
Fe_3O_4 + (P+K) + wheat	24.9	35.9	65.1
Fe_3O_4 + (P+N) + wheat	27.1	23.2	63.4
Fe_3O_4 + (N) + wheat	28.4	24.8	66.5

Let's visually examine the differences shown in the histograms.

Note: The Y-axis represents the chlorophyll content ($\mu\text{g/L}$).

Figure 10.

Histograms showing chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b contents in the control, P+K, P+N, and N groups.

The highest chlorophyll a content was observed in the P+K group, indicating the role of phosphorus and potassium in chlorophyll a biosynthesis (A).

A significant increase in chlorophyll b content was recorded in the N group, reflecting the stimulatory effect of nitrogen on chlorophyll b synthesis (B).

Figure 11. Histograms showing chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b contents in the Control, ZnO + wheat, and Fe₃O₄ + wheat groups.

Chlorophyll a levels in the ZnO + wheat group are similar to the Control (A), while a significant increase in chlorophyll b is observed in the Fe₃O₄ + wheat group (B). This may be related to the enhancement of chlorophyll b synthesis by Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles.

Figure 12. Histograms of chlorophyll a and b contents in Control and ZnO + fertilizer groups. A significant increase in chlorophyll a is seen in the ZnO + N group, indicating that zinc combined with nitrogen may enhance chlorophyll a synthesis (A). In contrast, other ZnO + fertilizer combinations show decreased chlorophyll b levels, suggesting potential negative effects on photosynthetic pigments (B).

Figure 13. Histograms showing chlorophyll a and b levels in the control and Fe₃O₄ + fertilizer combinations. Chlorophyll a content is close to or slightly higher than the control in all Fe₃O₄ combinations, whereas (A). Chlorophyll b content shows a marked increase in the Fe₃O₄ + (P+K) group. This result indicates that Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, especially when applied together with phosphorus and potassium, can stimulate chlorophyll b biosynthesis (B).

DISCUSSION

The results obtained in our study are consistent with previous research findings [5, 6]. Furthermore, the application of fertilizers enhanced the effect of nanoparticles and stimulated plant growth. In the groups treated with nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, germination rates increased; however, this was accompanied by weak development and low tillering in wheat treated with ZnO. The findings of this study indicate that the effects of ZnO and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles on plants depend on various factors, particularly concentration.

Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles and Their Mechanism of Action

Due to their magnetic properties, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are capable of regulating redox processes within plant cells. This balances intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels, enhances stress tolerance, and

stimulates metabolic activities [4, p. 1894]. The observed increase in chlorophyll b synthesis clearly demonstrates the role of Fe₃O₄ in the plant, emphasizing the importance of redox balance in pigment synthesis or stability. Thus, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles can enhance the efficiency of the photosynthetic process, thereby improving the overall photosynthetic performance of the plant.

The Role of ZnO Nanoparticles

Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles facilitate the effective uptake and transport of zinc, which is involved in essential metabolic processes such as photosynthesis and protein synthesis. Zinc functions as a cofactor for many enzymes and supports the functionality of photosynthetic complexes [3, p.185]. The observed increase in chlorophyll a levels in the study is related to ZnO's stimulation of the biosynthesis of primary photosyn-

thetic pigments. In particular, the stronger effect observed when ZnO was applied in combination with nitrogen (N) fertilizer suggests a synergistic interaction between zinc and nitrogen [12, p. 3808]. Nitrogen is a structural component of the chlorophyll molecule, and its presence enhances the effect of zinc on photosynthesis.

Interaction Between Nanoparticles and Fertilizers

The combined application of nanoparticles and fertilizers can produce either synergistic or antagonistic effects. For instance, in the ZnO + (P+N) group, both absorbance and chlorophyll content decreased. This may be due to the interaction between phosphorus and nitrogen elements with the nanoparticles inside the plant, potentially causing a metabolic imbalance [18]. Such cases highlight the importance of determining the optimal dosages of nanomaterials and macroelements, offering promising directions for future research.

General Conclusion

The two-stage study conducted allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the effects of nanoparticles (ZnO and Fe₃O₄) on the early developmental stages and photosynthetic potential of the wheat plant. Observations of germination and early development in the initial stage revealed that Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles significantly increased seed germination percentage and seedling height, while ZnO nanoparticles reduced these parameters compared to the control variant. This can be explained by their influence on cell wall permeability and metabolic activity.

In the second stage of the study, spectrophotometric analyses were used to evaluate the effects of ZnO and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles on the levels of chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b in wheat leaves. Based on the results, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles enhanced chlorophyll b synthesis, thereby increasing photosynthetic activity, while ZnO stimulated chlorophyll a biosynthesis, improving the plant's efficiency in utilizing light energy. These effects appeared in a more complex and selective manner when applied in combination with fertilizers, indicating that nanoparticles participate in plant metabolism through mechanisms of mutual interaction.

These findings demonstrate that nanoparticles have significant potential in agriculture for increasing crop productivity, enhancing resistance to plant stresses, and optimizing photosynthetic performance.

In future studies, it is essential to more precisely investigate the effects of these nanoparticles at different concentrations and under various environmental conditions. It is recommended that large-scale experiments be conducted to better analyze the effects of ZnO and Fe₃O₄, and that the positive and negative impacts of different nanoparticles on various plant species be compared.

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